

IMPORTANT STRATEGIES OF COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE TEACHING METHOD TO IMPROVE STUDENT’S SPEAKING ABILITY

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Abstract. *This article is devoted to CLT approach in enhancing speaking skills. Learners should be encouraged to take the initiative to participate and dare to express their ideas, it does not matter whether they use the language properly, but at least, they need to try and improve it through constant practice. Regarding strategies to develop English learners’ communicative competence; modeling, repetition, pair and group work were the most used ones. It is also necessary that students have a lot of exposure to the language, the linguistic input they receive should provide them with opportunities to produce and use the language at any situation, motivation then plays a very important role in encouraging students to verbally communicate.*

Keywords: *productive, accuracy, fluency, promote, interaction, modeling, simulations, elicitation, motivation.*

There are different methods that are being used to teach English as a foreign language but not all of them help us to reach the desired communicative goals; therefore, the selection and application of the most effective ones is required. All human beings need to communicate in order to express their ideas, feelings and thoughts, this is the main reason why communicative activities should be integrated into the lesson. Students spoken language is more productive when they are engaged in a dynamic learning environment that encourages them to do their tasks. It is well-known that all people need to understand spoken language in different situations, such as daily life, work, school, community, among others. According to Moss and Ross-Feldman [Moss, 2003], any activity which requires the learner to speak and listen to others includes the use of communication. Activities with communicative purposes are helpful for breaking down barriers, finding information, expressing ideas about oneself and learning about culture. Jeyasala asserts that teachers should encourage students’ communicative competence all the time, and besides their limitations to use language fluently and accurately, they should provide them with spaces to interact with others or to immerse them in speaking activities that enhance

their ability to use the target language. Providing students with real communicative contexts is the best option teachers can make, because students can exchange real information, so language and phrases will emerge according to the situation. It is also necessary that students have a lot of exposure to the language, the linguistic input they receive should provide them with opportunities to produce and use the language at any situation, motivation then plays a very important role in encouraging students to verbally communicate [Jeyasala, 2014].

According to Richards, learning the language does not always guarantee the learner will be able to use the language fluently. Consequently, the lack of fluency can be the result of rigid formal training in language learning; another reason can be the lack of strategies to involve students in communicative activities. Learners should be encouraged to take the initiative to participate and dare to express their ideas, it does not matter whether they use the language properly, but at least, they need to try and improve it through constant practice. The author also asserts that communicative competence involves the following aspects of language knowledge: knowing how to use the language in different situations, knowing how to vary the use of the language according to settings and participants (formal and informal speech), being able to understand different types of texts, and knowing how to maintain communication despite any limitation the speaker might have. When using communicative activities in the classroom, a distinction between fluency and accuracy should be done, understanding fluency as the natural language use that takes place when the speakers participate in a conversation despite the limitation of their communicative competence. Accuracy, on the other hand, refers to the creation of correct examples of language use. [Richards, 2006]

Interaction plays an important role in language learning since it gives the students the opportunity to put into practice their communication skills. In order to create meaningful interaction among learners, the correct materials that promote such interaction have to be chosen.

As Richards and Rodgers report, there is more information about Communicative language teaching than learning theory. For this reason, they believe that it is necessary to discuss about the three elements of the learning theory that can be distinguished in some communicative language teaching practices. The first element is the communication principle that relates to the activities focused on the use of real communication. The second is the task principle which focuses on the use of language to carry out meaningful tasks. Finally, the third one is the meaningfulness principle in which the language used must be meaningful to the learner. There is a great number of activities aimed at developing learners' communicative competence

using communicative processes, such as information sharing, negotiation of meaning, and interaction. Similarly, the use of games, role plays, simulations, and task-based communication activities are necessary to support classes in which the Communicative language teaching approach is used [Richards, 2014].

Similarly, Colker claims that students learn better by using their senses when they see, hear, touch, move, examine, smell, and even when they are provided with opportunities to taste things. She believes that students learn better when they have direct contact with the materials. Regarding strategies to develop English learners' communicative competence; modeling, repetition, pair and group work were the most used ones. Even though these strategies are used, their application in the English classroom is not providing the desired results because they were not used as frequent as they were necessary to provide learners with more opportunities to use the language to orally interact; therefore, it is necessary to use them more often and incorporate more strategies to help students develop communicative competence and enhance their active participation in oral activities. The findings also show that students are provided with metalinguistic and elicitation feedback to improve their communicative skills which allow learners to be aware of their mistakes while receiving input from the teacher through oral interaction.

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